

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ROLE OF STATE FISCAL (BUDGET-TAX) POLICY IN INCREASE OF POPULATION EMPLOYMENT

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Abstract

The main goal of the state is to achieve economic development by ensuring the well-being of the population. However, this cannot be achieved by itself, for this it is necessary to develop a reasonable economic policy by the state. The research of the priorities of the state fiscal (budget-tax) policy in achieving the economic growth of the society and ensuring the employment of the population is one of the urgent topics. The state fiscal (budget-tax) policy is aimed at increasing economic activity and eliminating problems in the economy through the rational use of state financial resources. Its main goal is to curb economic cycle fluctuations and inflation aimed at ensuring sustainable economic growth and achieving a high level of employment. The article provides scientific and practical analysis and conclusions aimed at ensuring employment of the population through the rational use of the economic levers of the state fiscal (budget-tax) policy.

Keywords: State fiscal (budget-tax) policy, employment, finance, state budget, state budget expenditures, state budget revenues, budget deficit, economic cycle, taxes, tax benefits.

Introduction

International Labor Organization experts recognize that the situation in the world, climate change, shortage of natural resources, and conflicts between countries may lead to a slowdown in global economic growth in 2023, and the population will be forced to accept working conditions that do not guarantee the minimum wage and social protection. The current situation, according to a new report by the experts of the International Labor Organization, will further increase the inequality that has already increased due to the pandemic [11]. Also, the International Labor Organization's report titled "World Employment and Social Protection Outlook: Trends to 2023" predicts that the global employment growth rate this year will be 1.0 percent. The number of unemployed worldwide is expected to reach 208 million in 2023 and the global unemployment rate will increase to 5.8 percent. The expectation of such a negative trend is directly related to the reduction of labor supply in high-income developed countries [12].

It is known that due to the pandemic, the cessation of economic activity, the closure of many workplaces and the worsening of the living conditions of the population, the return of most labor migrants to our country will lead to an increase in the number of unemployed. The lack of employment of the population, in turn, led to an increase in the level of unemployment and a decrease in the income of the population. Therefore, the state is conducting a consistent economic policy aimed at creating new jobs by encouraging active entrepreneurship, improving the investment climate and business environment. This includes the PF-27 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 28, 2023 On the state program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026 in the "year of human attention and quality education" adopted in the Republic of Uzbeki-

stan. PQ-214 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2022, "On additional measures to ensure employment of the population based on the development of the economy" decision, No. 450 decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated August 16, 2022, "On approval of the model concept for further increasing the efficiency of the assistants of district (city) mayors on the issues of developing entrepreneurship in the neighborhood, ensuring population employment, and reducing poverty", No. 450 decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2023 "On additional measures to support certain socially needy categories of the population and assist their employment", PF-61 dated April 26, 2023 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to support the employment of young people and provide them with permanent employment".

Also, in the republic, funds are provided from the state budget for the implementation of annually approved programs for ensuring the employment of the population, employment in vacant and quota jobs, and various tax benefits for the business sector that contributes to the employment of the population operating in the regions. However, there is still a high level of tension in the labor market in the regions, there are problems in establishing permanent jobs, ensuring employment of young people, women, members of low-income families, especially in rural areas, as well as in regulating the processes of external labor migration. This certainly shows the need to improve the mechanism of ensuring employment of the population, which is one of the economic policies of the state, the state fiscal policy, which is one of the factors of increasing economic activity. Also, rational distribution of state budget expenses and organization of economic activity that leads to activity in accordance with the level of development of the tax rates of the territories and thus ensuring the employment of the population is of great urgent importance.

Material and method.

It is known that the aspects of the state's fiscal (budget-tax) policy aimed at ensuring the employment and well-being of the population have been widely researched in the conditions of catastrophic risks and conflict situations that are still occurring in the world. It is known that in the history of economics, theoretical ideas aimed at providing employment of the population through the state treasury and taxes were formed by most representatives of the economic school. However, as an alternative to the classical economic school, the English economist J.M. Keynes in his world-famous work "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money" argued that the modern market economy is not capable of sustainable economic development, and to ensure sustainable economic growth and full employment of the population, the economy indicates that regulation by the state is necessary. One of the instruments of government regulation is fiscal policy, which affects the economy by changing government revenues and expenditures.[3]. It also shows two important problems of the market economy, namely, the inequitable distribution of income and the inability to provide full employment. Society does not stop developing, the economy moves to a new level of growth, but problems related to the labor market do not lose their relevance. Therefore, one of the important priorities of the state policy in the field of employment is to expand the demand for labor force, support employment, and support the effective use of labor resources in accordance with the requirements of the labor market.[9].

Harvard School of Economics representative P. Samuelson interprets fiscal policy as follows: Fiscal policy should help the economy smooth out cyclical fluctuations in the process of government taxation and government spending and achieve high employment free from excessive inflation and deflation. Also, the goal of fiscal policy, which depends on government spending and taxes, is to ensure high employment in the economy and a price process independent of inflation, in harmony with monetary policy.[7].

Theoretical views on the content of fiscal policy are supported by T.A.Agapov, S.F.Seregins from CIS economists. They understand that fiscal and monetary policies are government measures aimed at ensuring full employment, achieving balance of payments equilibrium, and ensuring economic growth in non-inflationary gross domestic product by changing public budget expenditures and taxes.[5].

Ensuring the employment of the population has always been one of the urgent issues. Especially in the context of the global pandemic, it has once again shown that the issue of employment is one of the global problems and requires more scientific research in this regard.

According to A.Olmasov and A.Vahobov, one of local economists, "Employment is the employment of people who have the ability to work and are eager to work, and engage in useful work"[8]. A.G. Gryaznov calls employment a set of economic relations related to employment and participation in economic activities. According to him, employment describes the economically active population concerned with the production

of material factors. In employment, the main productive and consuming forces of the society are manifested. Because the relationship to the objective conditions of production in it serves as a means of obtaining funds for the living of workers, which are considered to be the conditions of reproduction of the total population [1].

In addition to the results of these studies, scientifically based proposals, practical recommendations and conclusions, it is worth saying that the issue of the role and influence of the state fiscal policy in ensuring the employment of the population is considered, as well as determining its priorities.

Results

Active employment policies in most developed countries based on socially oriented market economies are aimed at achieving full, effective and freely chosen employment. Also, in the employment policy, the state's economic development should serve to achieve employment and other economic and social goals. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to take into account the interests of the state and take into account the national characteristics of the country based on real practice. Such actions should be carried out in coordination with the state, employers and recruits. The main task of the state is to regulate and control the mutual relations of partners in the labor market.

The state implements the following goals in ensuring full, effective and free employment of the population:

- develops tax, investment and financial and credit measures aimed at increasing the activity of labor resources, ensuring temporary and independent employment, coordinating labor activities and taking other measures, developing a system of job preservation and rational deployment of production forces;

- legal regulation of the legal rights and interests of citizens in the field of employment under the state guarantee and further improvement of employment legislation;

- social support for citizens recognized as unemployed.

In the employment policy, it is intended to provide employment to the part of the population that is able to work and wants to work, thereby creating an opportunity to provide them economically. In order to achieve these goals, the state tries to increase employment by creating new jobs in the country, using existing jobs effectively. Businesses that create new jobs are given tax breaks or subsidies. Also, by creating a new workplace, equipping it with modern technologies, it encourages achieving an increase in labor productivity and, accordingly, income. Depending on the severity of the employment problem, priority is given to one or another way of solving it. Priority is given to small business and private entrepreneurship, service industries, farmers and farms in creating new jobs in the employment policy of Uzbekistan.

Taxes, which are considered as components of the state fiscal policy in the economy, perform the following important tasks:

- financing of state expenses (fiscal function);

- distribution and redistribution of national income;
- alleviating social tension (social function);
- regulation of the economy (regulation function);
- stimulate economic activity.

According to the objective of the fiscal policy, stimulating its spontaneous growthlimiting, stabilization and economic activity policies are separated. Fiscal policy based on the goals of economic growth will increase the level of employment and thus the real volume of GDP is focused on growth. Stimulus fiscal policy in this levers of decrease in household expenses and tax rate is the decrease of State budget stability. Financial policy aimed at ensuring the decision about budget deficit during a recession or depression, it is necessary to focus on the goals of elimination.

The state's policy of limiting economic activity is sharply different from the potential level of real GNP – aimed at reducing the price, which at the same time, inflation and development during periods of economic growth and recession is focused on avoiding crisis processes in Rish.

Fiscal policy aimed at ensuring macroeconomic balance by regulating the cyclical development of the economy is carried out with the help of a number of financial instruments and economic levers. All these financial tools and levers together constitute the financial mechanism of regulation.

State fiscal policy, the tax system organized in the national economy. It is necessary to respond and effectively regulate internal relations in the economy. Fiscal policy of the state in the republic maintain the balance of the state budget at all scales[6].

As can be seen from the data of Figure 1, if we analyze the trend of changes in government expenditures and revenues in 2000-2022, the changes in state budget expenditures and revenues had a tendency to change in proportion to the growth rate of real GDP. In 2000, state budget revenues were 28.5 percent of GDP, and by 2022, they have decreased to 22.7 percent. In the same way, the state budget expenditure was 29.6 percent of GDP in 2000, and in 2022, this indicator decreased to 26.6 percent. If we analyze the growth rate of real GDP in our country, the lowest trend in 2000-2022 was observed in 2000 and 2020.

Figure 1. The impact of public fiscal policy on economic growth and employment[4]

In 2020, this indicator is guaranteed to grow by 1.6 percent despite the economic pandemic. The highest real GDP growth rates were observed in 2010, 2015 and 2016, when the growth rate averaged 8.0 percent. Correspondingly, state budget revenues and state budget

expenditures were about 21.0 percent of GDP. Analysis of the impact of changes in state budget expenditures and revenues on population employment is more clearly seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Impact of state budget expenditures and revenues on employment [14]

It should be noted that in 2000-2022, state budget expenditures and revenues and the impact on population employment have changed proportionally. The period with the highest weight of state budget revenues and expenses was observed in 2000, ie 28.5; It was 29.6 percent and, accordingly, the employment rate of the population reached 69.4 percent. Interestingly, such a high level of employment was also observed in 2015-2017. The lowest level of population employment was observed in 2020. Of course, this is directly related to the pandemic, but it decreased by 2.1% compared to 2019. If we take the weight of the employment level of the population in comparison with the indicator in 2019, it did not reach the level of this indicator in 2021-2022.

It should be noted that implementation of an effective state fiscal (budget-tax) policy in the Republic of

Uzbekistan for further strengthening the national economy and solving the emerging economic problems is one of today's requirements, once again confirmed by real practical life itself. As you know, in the world economy global economic growth is forecast to slow to 1.7 percent in 2023, one of the slowest in 30 years, trailing only the global recession of 2009 and 2020. This decline is due in part to the tightening of monetary policy to combat high inflation, which could cause negative shocks such as higher inflation, exchange rate tightening or financial turmoil to derail the global economy. Urgent action will be needed to reduce the risk of such a global crisis and debt crisis. In addition, governments should ensure that support is provided to the vulnerable, that inflation expectations remain stable and that financial systems remain stable.[2].

Figure 3. Global unemployment rate trend [13]

The reasons for the deterioration of the situation in the world labor market in this way are as follows:

- conflicts between states, increasing geopolitical tension;
- the unevenness of the recent economic recovery from the pandemic;
- continuing global supply problems.

It is worth noting that the combination of the above-mentioned factors created conditions for stagflation, that is, an increase in the rate of inflation and a slowdown in the economy at the same time. Such a situation is observed for the first time since 1970.

Richard Samens, director of the International Labor Organization's research activities department, noted that "slowing global employment growth means that we will not have to wait until 2025 to recover what

was lost during the Covid-19 pandemic." Also, in his opinion, the slowdown in productivity growth, which in his opinion is interdependent on solvency, environmental sustainability and population well-being, and which has been important in solving past crises, is of great concern[10].

Conclusions and suggestions

In our opinion, the state fiscal policy in the field of creating new jobs in our country should be improved on the basis of concrete methods, like foreign countries, to reduce unemployment and increase the employment of the population with socially necessary work. For this, we think that it is necessary to take into account the following measures: stimulation of investments made by the state in the economy, which is the main condition for creating new jobs;

Based on the above, it is necessary to improve the state fiscal policy to ensure the employment of the population in our country. It is appropriate to take into account the following:

1. In order to increase the employment of the population, first of all, it is necessary to effectively direct the state budget funds based on the level of unemployment in the regions and strictly control its implementation in practice.

2. It is necessary to reduce the level of the existing hidden economy in the republic and to fight against it, not by various bureaucratic means, but by using tax incentives according to the development potential of the regions.

3. It is necessary to use the practical experience of developed countries in applying tax incentives to large and small business entities that have created new jobs in the regions.

4. To create conditions on the basis of encouraging investment activity in small business and family entrepreneurship, to activate the job search of persons who have lost their jobs due to structural changes or are at risk of losing their jobs, providing them with vocational training, retraining and information-consulting services.

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